

Table 1. Weather record for rice flowering period at Los Baños (Agroclimatic Data Bank, IRRI).

Season	Flowering period (d)	Maximum temperature (°C)	Wind ^a		Relative humidity
			Speed (m/s)	Direction	
1987 WS (20-29 Nov)	1	23.9	2.1	ENE	55
	2	24.4	1.6	VRBL	78
	3	23.6	1.4	VRBL	81
	4	23.0	1.4	ESE	70
	5	24.0	1.3	NE	64
	6	24.2	1.7	NE	60
	7	22.9	5.2	WNW	62
	8	21.1	3.9	ENE	70
	9	23.0	1.7	SSE	57
	10	23.0	1.2	ESE	63
1988 DS (16-25 May)	1	36.2	1.2	NNW	42
	2	37.0	1.0	VRBL	34
	3	35.4	1.2	SE	42
	4	37.0	1.4	E	34
	5	36.5	1.1	S	42
	6	35.6	1.2	E	45
	7	35.0	0.9	VRBL	48
	8	36.5	1.2	SE	39
	9	33.4	1.1	NE	60
	10	34.5	1.2	NE	50

^a Expected wind direction in November and May is NE.

Table 2. Effect of distance between restorer line (R) and CMS line on outcrossing rate. IRRI, 1987 WS and 1988 DS.

Direction of CMS line in relation to pollen source	Distance (m) of CMS line from pollen source	Seed set ^a (%)	
		1987 WS	1988 DS
NE	0 (control)	9.2	8.6
	25	7.2	7.0
	50	6.0	5.0
	75	5.6	2.0
	100	5.0	0.5
	125	4.1	0.0
NW	150	3.8	0.0
	175	3.1	0.0
	200	2.4	0.0
	225	2.0	0.0
	0 (control)	6.0	4.0
	25	5.3	3.1
	50	5.1	1.2
	75	4.0	0.3
	100	3.3	0.0
	125	2.1	0.0
	150	0.8	0.0
	175	0.0	0.0
	200	0.0	0.0
	225	0.0	0.0

^a Av of 4 replications.

complete pollen sterility were retained per distance (each plant represented one replication). The potted plants were kept in the field for 10 d (20-29 Nov in 1987 wet season [WL] and 16-25 May in 1988 dry season [DS]) to synchronize with flowering of the pollen source. No other flowering rice crop was around the field for more than 500 m in any direction. Distance pollen traveled was determined

by seed setting on open-pollinated panicles of the CMS line.

In 1987 WS, seed set on CMS plants up to 225 m distance in the northeast direction and up to 150 m in the northwest direction (Table 2). In 1988 DS, seed set on CMS plants up to 100 m in the northeast direction and up to 75 m in the northwest direction. Pollen traveled farther in WS than in

DS, perhaps because of higher wind velocity (1.2-5.2 m/s in WS, 0.9-1.4 m/s in DS). Higher temperature, lower relative humidity, and unfavorable wind direction in DS may have cut the distance pollen could travel. Under Los Baños conditions, a safe isolation distance would be 125 m in DS and 250 m in WS. □

CNA-IRAT 4, a new CMS indica rice population

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CNPAP and Institut de Recherches Agronomiques Tropicales et des Cultures Vivrières (IRAT) have created an indica population that segregates for a monogenic recessive male sterile gene obtained by mutation on IR36 by R. J. Singh and H. Ikehashi.

Nine varieties were crossed and backcrossed to IR36 as the male parent to achieve sterile plants (see table). F₂ seeds of each backcross were bulked to

CNA-IRAT 4 population composition.

Variety	Parentage	Outcrossing rate (%)
IR36 (ms ms)	IR1561-228-1-2/IR1737//CR94-13	25.00
BG90-2	IR262/Remadja	8.33
CNA7	T141/IR665-1-175-3	8.33
CNA3815	CICA4/BG90-2/SML 5617	8.33
CNA3848	5461//IR36/CICA7	8.33
CNA3887	4440//BG90-2/Tetep	8.33
Colombia 1	Napal/Takao Iku 18	8.33
Eloni	IR454/SML KAPURI//SML 66H10	8.33
Nanicao	Brazilian germplasm	8.33
UPR103-80-1-2	IR24/Cauvery	8.33

form the initial population, CNA-IRAT 4/0/0.

Outcrossed seeds collected on male sterile plants of that population were bulked to form the next population, CNA-IRAT 4/0/1. The procedure was

repeated four times to obtain the CNA-IRAT 4/0/4 population.

Seeds of the CNA-IRAT 4/0/4 population are available to rice breeders. □